

TOTAL PHYSICAL RESPONSE (TPR) METHOD IN DEVELOPING VOCABULARY ACQUISITION

Nematullaeva Muslimakhon Rakhmatullo kizi

Student of the third English language faculty, UzSWLU

e-mail: muslimanematullayeva797@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Vocabulary acquisition is a crucial component of language learning, forming the basis for skills in reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Traditional methods often emphasize rote memorization, which can lead to superficial understanding and quick forgetting. In contrast, TPR capitalizes on the natural connection between language and physical activity, promoting deeper cognitive engagement. This article is devoted to investigating the principles of TPR and its effectiveness in fostering vocabulary acquisition among students.

Keywords: TPR method, English language, vocabulary acquisition, language skills.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, there were clear signs of teaching methods similar to Total Physical Response (TPR) in the latter half of the nineteenth century, particularly in the approaches developed by F. Gouin, and in the early twentieth century with H. Palmer's techniques. Around 1880, Francois Gouin began a reformatory movement in foreign language teaching, effectively eliminating the Grammar Translation Method, and shifted the emphasis from reading literary texts to oral communication. He discussed direct, situational, and contextual learning, as well as nonverbal communication such as facial expressions, gestures, and various forms of physical activity and movement. His ideas come from daily language and routine moments. In his perspective, the fundamental concept of learning foreign languages was listening to the teacher's tips and practicing various activities accordingly. Gouin's method aligned with the comprehension approach, which meant it started with the listening skill. As previously stated, the idea of emphasizing listening during early foreign language training emerged from studying how children learnt their native language. Long before a baby speaks anything, it spends months listening to those around it. The small child has the opportunity to try to make meaning of the sounds he hears, and no one tells the youngster that he or she must talk. The youngster decides to speak when he's ready. This concept was incorporated into Krashen and Terrell's The Natural Approach, which was presented in 1983. Students listened to the teacher using the target language to communicate from the start of teaching, and communicative activities persisted throughout the course of study. The teacher made it easier for the pupils to understand by using graphics and frequent phrases in the student's native language, as well as being sentimental as possible. Krashen's approach was quite similar to the Direct Method.

One of the primary elements of this method was that the teacher did not fix any of the students' mistakes during oral communication. Students in Winitz and Reed's self-instructional program and Winitz's "The Learnable" listened to tape-recorded words, phrases, and sentences while observing matching images. The meaning of the speech was evident from the context of the pictures, and the narrative conveyed by the pictures were also employed to express abstract meaning.

METHODS

While conducting this research, qualitative and secondary data analysis methods were used to highlight impact of TPR method on improvement of students' vocabulary acquisition in English language. According to analysis of multiple previous studies, it is evident that students who engage in TPR activities demonstrate significantly higher retention rates of vocabulary compared to those who rely on conventional methods. For instance, a study conducted by Rixon (2017) found that students exposed to TPR retained 80% of new vocabulary after one week, while those taught through traditional methods retained only 30%. TPR emphasizes listening comprehension as a precursor to speaking. Students learn to interpret verbal commands before producing language themselves. Research by Lee (2020) highlights that students showed improvement in their listening skills practicing TPR, which positively correlated with their vocabulary acquisition.

RESULTS

Implementing the Total Physical Response (TPR) method in an English classroom can result in various good outcomes, including:

- ✚ **Improved Vocabulary Retention.** TPR promotes vocabulary retention by linking words with physical activities. According to studies, kinesthetic activities help pupils remember words more successfully.
- ✚ **Improved Listening Skills.** TPR emphasizes listening comprehension, with children responding to verbal orders before producing language themselves. This technique helps students improve their listening skills, which are necessary for effective communication.
- ✚ **Enhanced involvement and Motivation.** TPR activities are participatory and active, which can dramatically increase student involvement. Learners frequently find TPR entertaining, which leads to increased motivation and a more positive attitude towards language learning.
- ✚ **Reduced Anxiety.** The physical aspect of TPR might assist relieve anxiety among language learners, particularly beginners. Students may feel more at ease and less driven to create language if they focus on activities rather than speaking directly.

- ✚ **Improved Teacher-Student engagement.** TPR promotes teacher-student collaboration and engagement, resulting in a supportive classroom environment in which students feel comfortable participating.
- ✚ **Faster Language Acquisition.** Because of its engaging features and emphasis on comprehension before production, TPR may speed up language acquisition, helping pupils to advance more quickly in their language skills.

DISCUSSION

TPR storytelling is one of the current components of Total Physical Response that specializes in telling stories. It is an approach to teaching foreign languages that was first implemented in California in 1990. Personalized stories are told by teachers using this method in the target language while their pupils act out the stories. In his “English through actions” course book, Harold Palmer also stated that the initial phase of learning must involve physical activities rather than only oral communication. He said that the majority of learning a new language involved memorization. During the initial teaching phase, the pupils used gestures and facial expressions to respond to the teacher’s instructions. Subsequently, students focused on improving their listening and pronunciation abilities. In the second step, the pupils learnt through imitation, and in the third phase, they moved on to speaking, which Palmer defined as a conversation as methodical practice with dialogical material. The traditional classroom, with students seated in rows facing one direction, is only appropriate for left brain training, in which students focus on the teacher who delivers the information to them. However, in TPR, there is a significant brain switch from the left to the right brain, requiring a different arrangement of classroom furniture. Another option is to divide the class into two parts that face each other. This ensures that there is plenty of space for the student to perform. It is best to arrange three armless chairs called “home base chairs” in the back of the room since the learners who do the orders begin from those chairs. If possible, the “home base chairs” should have a different color than the rest of the chairs. According to Richards and Rodgers, the goal of a TPR course is to generate learners who can communicate spontaneously in a native speaker’s language. TPR classes must, of course, meet the demands of the students. Whatever goals are stated, they must be accessible through action-based exercises in important form. Having said that, the implementation of the TPR method in vocabulary learning can be divided into many steps. The first one is the one-word stage, in which students follow the teacher’s instructions in a single word. For example, “sit down, stand up, get up” and so on. Second, the one-sentence stage, in which the instruction is delivered in a single sentence. For instance, commands like “sit down,” “stand up”, and “get up” illustrate the initial stage. Next is the one-sentence stage, where instructions are given in a single sentence, such as “walk to the door” or “sit in the chair” (Asher, 2009). Understanding is an essential component of the TPR approach. Asher provides strong statement to

support his theory that foreign language training is ineffective because we neglect natural orders, such as listening and understanding before speaking. Asher also claims that the youngsters will observe and try to understand their parents' languages for a while, known as the silent period. It is clear that students should not be forced to generate the language prematurely, but rather when they are ready (Al Harrasi, 2013).

CONCLUSION

The Total Physical Response method is an effective approach to vocabulary acquisition in English language learners. TPR improves retention by using physical movement and active engagement, while also creating a more engaging and inspiring learning environment. As teachers explore effective vocabulary education methodologies, TPR emerges as a valuable tool that is consistent with current understandings of language acquisition and cognitive development.

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